

FORMATIVE CONTENT AND SOCIAL SIGNIFICANCE OF FICTION

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ABSTRACT

This article mentions the dual nature of fiction, that it is an art phenomenon on the one hand, and a form of social consciousness on the other. Now, why fiction is said to belong to the sphere of social consciousness, to itself as a form of social consciousness characteristic is described.

KEYWORDS: *Economic, Spirituality, Improvement, Formation, Ideas, the Embodiment of Knowledge and Skills, Socio-Economic, Initiative, Efficiency, From Antiquity to the Present.*

INTRODUCTION

It is known that at the core of the reforms implemented in our country is the human factor and human value. In this sense, enjoying the modern achievements of science and education, along with receiving spiritual and educational knowledge, is of great importance in the formation of a real person.

Fundamental development of the system of higher education institutions and secondary special social and economic educational institutions, social economy and spiritual foundations, national ideas, historical philosophical theory of our nation, students of social humanitarian education. is intended for, along with acquiring theoretical knowledge, strengthening knowledge and skills on the basis of practical and laboratory experience, artistic, literary, pedagogical and psychological, socio-economic, spiritual foundations, human factor, essay law, domestic labor fields, the material and spiritual living conditions of people, the importance of fiction in the spiritual growth of a person, philosophical analysis, historical pages, the science of human education, its laws, thoughts through the study of pedagogy, new ideas, knowledge and skills In its embodiment, it determines the giving of initial knowledge, skills and qualifications regarding the interest in fiction, the place of our country on the world scale.

The process of teaching the experience gained at work to the younger generation, while the businessmen of our country learn the working methods of the developed countries, the ability to independently use modern innovative new equipment, young designers, working with young people who have a high level of educational ability, requires achieving high results. .

This article brings to life educational and qualification processes aimed at socio-economic, spiritual growth of people, strengthening the level of education, enthusiastic attitude to work, conscious choice of profession, imagination and thinking of mental and physical work for the welfare of society and individual. Emphasizes the necessity of implementation.

Advanced thinking circles and changes in the students, the result of scientific research, and the effect of the ongoing reforms are aimed at the spiritual growth of our people and raising the level

of knowledge. As a result of improving the level of knowledge as a result of relying on practical experiences along with the improvement of theoretical knowledge, efforts are made to reach higher heights. It is necessary to have the qualities of knowledge, activity, initiative, efficiency and organization, talent, discipline and sense of responsibility and responsibility.

Fundamental development of the educational system, higher and secondary special social and economic educational institutions for students of social economy and spiritual foundations, national ideas, philosophical theory, social humanitarian education is designed to strengthen knowledge and skills based on practical experience along with acquiring theoretical knowledge, artistic, literary, pedagogical, socio-economic, spiritual foundations, human factor, domestic labor spheres, material and spiritual living conditions of people, the importance of fiction in the spiritual growth of a person, philosophical analysis, the science of human education, its laws, interest in fiction in the embodiment of thoughts, ideas, knowledge and skills through the study of pedagogy, the place of our country in the world determines the provision of initial knowledge, skills and qualifications. The process of teaching the young generation the experiences gained in work, while the entrepreneurs of our country learn the working methods of the developed countries, the ability to independently use modern innovative new equipment, young designers, working with young people who have a high level of educational ability requires achieving high results.

Relevance of the Topic

This reflected article is a product of training and qualification processes aimed at enthusiastic attitude to work, conscious choice of profession, imagination and thinking of mental and physical work for the welfare of society and individual. Fundamental changes in students, renewal of pages, and the effect of the ongoing reforms are aimed at raising the standard of living of our people to the ranks of highly developed democratic states.

As a result of the active participation of the listeners, they develop such moral qualities as social attitude to work careful preservation and saving of public property, respect and love for working people. Activity, initiative, planning, organization, discipline and sense of responsibility, as well as education of mutual help are the main tasks of today.

A number of changes in social and economic spheres in our country, world tourism, mutual cooperation with developed countries, implementation of import-export, trade, gas processing, development of electricity system, bringing modern investments from neighboring countries to our territory. Development of production based on input and demand, expansion of jobs in the country is an urgent task of today.

It is necessary to develop the field of education, among the tasks set in the field of education, to eliminate the worldview and scientific potential of our youth, the huge changes that occurred in our country during the years of independence, and the scale of existing problems. Today, it is the result of the reforms and plans that are being implemented to achieve our great goals and noble deeds, the renewal of our society, the development and perspective of our life. We all understand that all this is closely related to the problem of training highly qualified and conscious specialists who meet the requirements of the time.

As a result of the gradual transition of our republic to the market economy and comprehensive penetration into the world community, there are demands to deepen learning and improve the level of education of students. The opportunities and privileges created in accordance with the law open up new prospects for the development of intellectual property innovation processes based on increasing economic efficiency in the effective use of intellectual property, mastering new techniques and technologies, and using them to produce new products.

A collection of works summarizing achievements in a certain field of literature is technical literature, agricultural literature, political literature, etc. A type of art is also called fiction; reflects reality through images using words. Literature was originally in oral form, and as a result of the appearance of writing, it began to be written.

Literature has the ability to widely and deeply reflect human feelings through words; therefore it is considered the most popular form of art. There are 3 leading types of fiction - epic, lyric, drama. The epic perceives the reality itself, and the lyric describes the impressions of the person from the reality. The East has long been a land of poetic feelings. For this reason, especially lyricism is widely developed in the literary literature of the East. Drama expresses life in action without the author's speech.

When we say fiction, we mean the artistic world consisting of the works of advanced and progressive writers. The first task of literature for the advanced representatives of Eastern and Western literature, which has continued from ancient times to the present, is to create a true artistic vision of life. When we say life, we mean the life of the country, society, people and some individuals. In the process of artistic reflection of life, fiction confirms the beauty and goodness in this life, serves to write wings of new and advanced principles in the life of society and people.

The important tasks of fiction are to create an image of a person, to describe his inner world, to show the budding and flowering of the buds of beauty in his nature and spirit under the influence of the external world. But fiction, as a school of example, not only reflects the life, man and his spiritual world, but also describes the beauty in nature and the psyche of people, the exemplary events of the historical past, as well as the present and the present. by reflecting people's lives, it is to have an emotional impact on people, to give them pleasure, to educate them, and to actively participate in their formation as well-rounded people. Fiction differs from other types of literature in these aspects. Every person familiar with fiction will enjoy the beauty of nature and society more. A person who reads a book, no matter what field he works in, will have the ability to think correctly, distinguish between black and white, and make wise decisions in complex situations. In addition, his speech is fluent; he can get people to follow him.

A book is an unquenchable light that illuminates the paths of life, a source of happiness that gives meaning to a person's life, a loyal friend that accompanies him in any situation. There is no tool as powerful as a book to ensure the spiritual maturity of a person. That is why, from time immemorial, enlightened leaders and wise men have called all mankind to read books and learn the secrets of science and manners from them. The book is a great power that lifts a person from earth to heaven and increases his spiritual power. It is a foundation that strengthens the historical memory, spiritual and educational world, scientific ground of mankind, and shows the bright future.

A friend like a book contains all the knowledge that keeps people aware of the past and the future. The book is a great power that lifts a person from earth to heaven and increases his spiritual power. It is a factor that strengthens the historical memory of mankind, the spiritual and educational world, and the scientific ground.

Today, the state pays special attention to the development of reading culture in our society, especially among young people, and a lot of effective work is being done. Including the President

Decree of January 12, 2017 "On the establishment of a commission for the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, increase and promotion of book reading and reading culture", September 13, 2017 "Publishing and distribution of book products on the program of comprehensive measures to develop the system, increase and promote book reading and reading culture" and on May 12, 2018 "Wide study and promotion of the creative heritage of our great scholars, writers and thinkers The implementation of a number of organizational and practical measures aimed at developing the culture of reading in our country on the basis of the decision "On organizing reading contests among young people for the purpose of making.

Educational programs, study guides and literature are organized in higher education institutions in cooperation with supervisors established in the university itself. The president is promoting the importance of reading books among young people and leaders.

The comprehensive solution of such important tasks, which are of great importance in improving our spiritual life, improving the system of publication and distribution of book products, placing the best examples of Uzbek and world literature on the Internet and promoting them to a wide readership. effective organization of delivery work, preservation of the rich spiritual heritage of our great scholars, writers and thinkers who grew up in our ancient and unique land, the unique works of our great ancestors who made a great contribution to the development of universal civilization, culture, secular and religious science, and to future generations to convey their rare heritage, exemplary life and social activity in every way and promote, educate our youth in the spirit of self-awareness, national and universal values, popularize the reading culture among them.

CONCLUSION

The result of literary education without artistic analysis of the text of a literary work is a person without spirituality, an expert without knowledge. Since the renewed national pedagogy has set itself the goal of forming highly spiritual individuals, it is important that artistic analysis is of decisive importance in literary education. In the absence of qualified artistic analysis, the magic, mystery, charm of a miraculous work disappears. Because the artistic and vital meaning behind it remains unnoticed.

Like any branch of science, the science of "Fundamentals of Artistic Analysis" has its own research methods. For example, research methods such as observation, proof, generalization, evaluation, axiology, conditionality, comparativistic, mental reasoning, artistic value determination, comparison, generalization, heuristic, etc. are used to collect, summarize, analyze, systematize and are the methods used in reaching a certain scientific conclusion. Some of these

research methods can be used in the investigation of other disciplines, but in this case they are used for a different purpose and purpose.

A philologist who does not fully understand the literary text cannot achieve the expected results during his activities aimed at shaping the spirituality of other people. However, philologists are professionals who are responsible for shaping the spirituality of the people of the nation. The reason why fiction has a high rank in the lives of members of the society, and why literature has a special privileged position in the education system comes from its great social importance. Noble spirituality, high moral values are formed by mastering experiences in this direction. Of course, not everyone has to experience this kind of experience.

Before answering questions such as what does the concept of "analysis of a work of art" mean, how is artistic analysis carried out, in what ways should it be materialized, the basic concept that gave rise to all these questions - the term "work of art" is correct it is appropriate to come to a certain conclusion.

Because the book is a tool of thinking, a key to treasures, a source of thought, our people considered it as dear, honorable and sacred as bread. That is why love for books, appreciation of them, desire to read is ingrained in the blood of our people. A person's culture is reflected in his book. In this sense, today, reading books and the attitude towards them seem to have weakened somewhat. Because young people are more addicted to movies, videos, television, and computers. Any new information can be obtained from these tools as desired. It's a pity that there is no need to spend time reading a book today. In fact, no media, film or video can replace a work of art. No matter how skillfully the movies are filmed, they cannot convey the effect and charm of the book. Reading also depends on the family environment. In enlightened families, attention to books is useful in raising children.

We know that man differs from other creatures in his thinking ability, spiritual world, and theory of consciousness. One of the factors that distinguish a person from other creatures is his consciousness and spirituality. Only truly patriotic people with high intellectual potential, independent worldview, initiative, physically healthy and spiritually mature people are the decisive force of the reforms being carried out in the system today, the true defenders of our people. In the formation of the above positive qualities for citizens of the society, it is important for them to be familiar with books, to expand their knowledge and outlook by reading books of various genres, not only related to their professional activities. In Uzbekistan, starting from 2021, the first week of April is designated as "Book Reading Week".

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. In accordance with paragraph 13 of the statement No. 19 of the video selector meeting held on March 4 of this year under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev.
2. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 13, 2017 No. PQ-3271.
3. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. 781 dated 14.12.2020.
4. Myself. The first volume. Tashkent, 2000.